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**WWRF52
King's
College
London, UK**

10-12 September 2024

Location

CFP for WWRF52

Call for Papers

Global Nexus: Universal Communications, Intelligence & Sustainability

52nd Wireless World Research Forum

King's College, London, UK
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The key three pillars of next-generation mobile communication networks are sustainability, universal communications (in terms of both connectivity and digital inclusion), and network intelligence. Within that context, new types of capabilities are anticipated through native network intelligence, the tight integration of sensing functionalities and a commitment to sustainability. These key pillars of beyond 5G networks create an exciting albeit challenging field of research with the potential to significantly impact not only our everyday daily lives but a diverse set of industries. To this end, the emerging efforts towards the definition and initial steps towards the standardization of the next-generation wireless networks aim to integrate terrestrial, aerial, and satellite systems to ensure a truly seamless, global coverage in a unified manner in terms of terminal and overall end-user experience. Next generation networks will leverage advanced distributed intelligence, enabling real-time data processing and real-time decision-making, enhancing both personal and industrial applications. Sustainability is also at the forefront, with green technologies and energy-efficient protocols designed to minimize the environmental footprint in the era of climate crisis and net-zero commitment across different industries. Consequently, a complex ecosystem of networks, interconnected applications, services, and physical/virtual devices, with a high degree of heterogeneity, emerges. This heterogeneity is envisioned to be tamed by native network ML/AI solutions that must display significant levels of autonomy in terms

Important Dates

Abstract Deadline:	31 st July 2024
Notification of Acceptance:	8 th August 2024
Early registration:	22 nd August 2024
Final paper and Copyright Licence Submission:	3 rd September 2024
Event:	10 th -12 th September 2024

King's College London

- ❑ King's College London is one of England's oldest and most prestigious universities, founded within the tradition of the Church of England by King George IV and the Duke of Wellington who granted our royal charter in 1829.
- ❑ King's has a proud history of inspiring and supporting those who seek to solve the world's most pressing problems.
- ❑ For almost 200 years, our community has been deeply rooted in the belief that learning and research should serve society.

Entrance

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**We are looking forward to seeing
you in London!**

